

TECHNICAL SCIENCES

DETERMINATION OF THE DEPENDENCE OF THE STRESS AMPLITUDE IN A PIPELINE ON THE FREQUENCY OF A LONGITUDINAL WAVE IN SOIL USING A NUMERICAL METHOD

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ABSTRACT

The results of numerical solutions of coupled problems on longitudinal wave propagation in interacting composite long rods are presented. The wave equations for the inner and outer rods are coupled by non-linear interaction forces at their contact surface. With zero initial and boundary conditions, the problem is solved by the method of characteristics followed by the application of the finite difference method. In the case when the outer rod (soil) is less strong than the inner rod (a pipeline), a high increase in the longitudinal stresses in the inner rod was observed compared to the stress amplitude in soil. The dependence of the stress amplitude in the pipeline on the frequency of the longitudinal wave in soil was established.

Keywords: soil, seismic waves, stresses, finite difference method, composite rods, underground pipeline.

Introduction

The propagation of longitudinal shock and continuous waves in composite elastic rods interacting according to the Coulomb dry friction law was studied in [1], where the patterns of changes in wave parameters in the considered rods were obtained. In [2], changes in the parameters of waves in composite elastic and viscoelastic rods interacting according to complex nonlinear laws were studied. In [3], this problem was considered in relation to the problem of seismic resistance of underground pipelines in the case of high-frequency longitudinal waves. The purpose of this article is to study the patterns of propagation of low-frequency waves in composite elastic and viscoelastic rods. Nonlinear laws of interaction were given and discussed in [4, 5]. The method for solving coupled nonlinear wave problems was discussed in [1–3, 6, 7].

In [8], a one-dimensional formulation of a nonstationary wave problem was presented, focusing on the propagation and reflection of a longitudinal monochromatic wave from a rigid, immobile barrier in contact with an underground pipeline. The pipeline's deformation behavior was modeled using the linear viscoelastic Eyring model, which accounts for constrained creep and relaxation processes. The problem was solved numerically by applying the method of characteristics, followed by the finite difference method using an implicit scheme.

In most cases, the reliability of underground main pipelines is evaluated based on their structural strength [9]. When assessing the strength of such pipelines under seismic loads, it is essential to account for the longitudinal interaction forces between the pipe and the surrounding soil, specifically frictional forces. As demonstrated in [9], these interaction forces at the pipe-soil interface exhibit a complex behavior influenced by the characteristics of wave propagation in both the soil and the pipeline.

Using numerical solutions to one-dimensional, non-stationary coupled wave problems for the "underground pipeline-soil" interaction system, the distribution and variation of contact forces along the pipe-soil

interface were determined. The study revealed that incorporating both static and dynamic components of soil pressure normal to the contact surface yields significantly different results compared to considering static pressure alone. The findings highlight the importance of accounting for the dynamic stress-strain state of the soil surrounding the pipeline when evaluating the reliability of underground main pipelines subjected to seismic excitation.

The study examined numerical results expressed as dependencies of wave parameters—longitudinal stress, velocity, and strain—at fixed points along the pipeline. The analysis revealed that at high frequencies of the dynamic load inducing the wave, the stress amplitude within the pipeline increases significantly—often by a factor of two or more—relative to the amplitude of the applied load. This effect is attributed to the superposition of incident and reflected waves, as well as the rapid rate of loading. In contrast, at low loading frequencies, this amplification does not occur due to the slower loading rate.

The numerical results obtained provide a basis for formulating dynamic stress analysis problems for underground pipelines depending on the frequency of the incident wave. It was shown that the maximum longitudinal stresses occur at locations near the pipeline's connection to the rigid, stationary structure.

In [10], the propagation of longitudinal waves in a viscoelastic medium was analyzed. A mathematical model describing a linear viscoelastic medium was formulated, and the problem was transformed into a system of differential equations. These equations were solved using the method of characteristics, subject to appropriate boundary conditions. The obtained results were compared with previously published data from other researchers, confirming the validity of the proposed model. It was found that the peak values of stress, strain, and particle velocity in the viscous medium follow a nonlinear pattern. In the initial region of the medium and its vicinity, the stress reaches its maximum first, followed by the peak values of strain and particle velocity.

In [11], numerical solutions to the nonlinear wave problem involving longitudinal wave propagation are presented. The soil is modeled as an external rod, within which a wave is initiated. The internal rod responds to frictional forces that develop at the contact interface between the two rods, with these forces governed by complex nonlinear relationships. The study investigates how the stability of the numerical solutions depends on the time and space discretization steps. Optimal discretization parameters are identified to ensure the stability and reliability of the computed results.

In [12], focuses on the investigation of longitudinal wave propagation in a nonlinear viscoelastic medium. A mathematical formulation of the problem is presented using the equation of motion behind the wave front, expressed in Lagrangian coordinates. The problem was addressed using the method of characteristics.

Through the analysis of specific cases, it was found that the amplitude of the initial stress oscillation at fixed points in the medium exceeds that of subsequent oscillations. Additionally, structural changes in the medium under deformation were shown to be highly sensitive to the strain rate. It was also observed that the damping coefficient, which is linearly dependent on wave frequency, exhibits significant variation across a broad frequency range.

Main part

A semi-infinite coaxial composite rod is considered. The initial sections of the rods $x=0$ coincide (x is the spatial coordinate coinciding with the axis of the rods). The strength characteristics of the rods differ significantly. The inner rod is a model of a straight main steel pipeline, and the outer rod is a model of soil. Similar to [1, 3], the composite rod is assumed to be the simplest model of an underground pipeline surrounded by soil.

The equations of motion of the rod and soil, taking into account the interaction force (friction), have the following form

$$\begin{aligned} \rho_{0i} \partial v_i / \partial t - \partial \sigma_i / \partial x + \chi_i \sigma_{\tau i} &= 0 \\ \partial v_i / \partial x - \partial \varepsilon_i / \partial t &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where v_i is the particle velocity (mass velocity); σ_i , ε_i are longitudinal stresses and strains; ρ_{0i} is the initial density for the rod – $\chi_i = \text{sign}(v)$ and for soil – $\chi_i = -\text{sign}(v)$; $v = v_1 - v_2$ is the relative velocity; σ_{τ} is the reduced friction force acting per unit length of the rod; t is time. The values of σ_{τ} for the rod and soil are determined from the following relationship:

$$\sigma_{\tau i} = 4D_{Hi} \tau / (D_{Hi}^2 - D_{Bi}^2) \quad (2)$$

where τ is the friction force (shear stress) between the rod and soil; D_{Hi} are the external diameters of the rod and soil; D_{Bi} are the internal diameters of the pipeline and soil.

The equations of state of the rod and soil are assumed to be linear-viscoelastic (a standard-linear body):

$$\frac{d\varepsilon_i}{dt} + \mu_i \varepsilon_i = \frac{d\sigma_i}{E_{Di} dt} + \mu \frac{d\sigma_i}{iE_{Si}} \quad (3)$$

$$\mu_i = E_{Di} E_{Si} / (E_{Di} - E_{Si}) \eta_i$$

Here and below, $i=1, 2$. For $i=1$, the values of the parameters refer to the rod, and for $i=2$, they refer to soil.

The solution to the problem is reduced to integrating system (1) closed by equation (3) separately for the rod ($i=1$) and separately for soil ($i=2$). This system is coupled by conditions on the contact surface of the rod and soil, which determine the laws of change in the friction force.

The friction law based on the model of a standard-linear body and Coulomb's law for $\sigma_N > \sigma_N^*$ (for $\sigma_N \leq \sigma_N^*$, τ) are represented by the following relations

$$\text{for } 0 \leq u \leq u_*$$

$$\begin{aligned} &\frac{d\tau}{K_x^D(\sigma_N, I_S) dt} + \\ &+ \mu_S(\sigma_N, I_S, \dot{u}) \frac{\tau}{K_x^S(\sigma_N, I_S)} = \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

$$= \frac{du}{dt} + \mu_S(\sigma_N, I_S, \dot{u}) u$$

$$\text{for } du/dt \geq 0, \quad u > u_*$$

$$\tau = f_u \sigma_N, \quad (5)$$

$$\text{for } du/dt < 0, \quad u \geq u_*$$

$$\tau = 0, \quad (6)$$

where $K_x^D(\sigma_N, I_S)$ is the function of dynamic interaction (as $\dot{u} \rightarrow \infty$), and $K_x^S(\sigma_N, I_S)$ is the function of quasi-static interaction (as $\dot{u} \rightarrow 0$); μ_S is the function of soil shear viscosity parameter related to soil shear viscosity function $\eta_S = (\sigma_N, I_S, \dot{u})$ by the following relationship:

$$\mu_S = K_x^D K_x^S / (K_x^D - K_x^S) \eta_S \quad (7)$$

The nature of the interaction functions K_x^D , K_x^S , and K_x^R and the parameters entering them are given in [4, 5].

The wave is formed in the initial section $x=0$ by a load that changes according to the following law:

$$\sigma_i = \sigma_{\max} \sin(2\pi t/T) \quad 0 \leq t \leq \theta, \quad (8)$$

where σ_{\max} is the amplitude, T is the oscillation period, θ is the load action time.

Boundary conditions are: conditions (8) are fulfilled in the initial section of soil; $\sigma_1 = 0$ – in the initial section of the rod; and at the wave front in the rod, they are:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_1 &= -C_{01}\rho_{01}v_1; \\ v_1 &= -C_{01}\varepsilon_1; \end{aligned} \tag{9}$$

$$C_{01} = (E_{D1} / \rho_{01})^{1/2}$$

and at the wave front in soil they are:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_2 &= -C_{02}\rho_{02}v_2; \\ v_2 &= -C_{02}\varepsilon_2; \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

$$C_{02} = (E_{D2} / \rho_{02})^{1/2}$$

where C_{0i} are the velocities of the wave front in the rod and in soil, respectively.

The calculations were conducted using the developed computer program for the numerical solution to equations (1) – (3) considering (4) – (10), using the method of characteristics, followed by the finite difference method.

The following was chosen as initial data:

For steel underground pipeline (a rod)	For soil	Seismic load parameters	Interaction parameters
$D_{H1} = 0.2 \text{ m};$ $D_{B1} = 0.18 \text{ m};$ $\rho_{01} = 7800 \text{ kg/m}^3;$ $\mu_1 = 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1};$ $C_{01} = 5000 \text{ m/s};$ $\gamma_1 = 1.02;$ $E_{D1} = C_{01}^2 \rho_{01};$ $E_{S1} = E_{D1} / \gamma_1;$	$\rho_{01} = 1800 \text{ kg/m}^3;$ $C_{01} = 1000 \text{ m/s};$ $K_\sigma = 0.3;$ $\mu_2 = 1000 \text{ s}^{-1};$ $\gamma_2 = 1.1;$ $E_{D2} = C_{02}^2 \rho_{02};$ $E_{S2} = E_{D2} / \gamma_2;$	$T = 0.01 \text{ s};$ $\theta = 5 \text{ s};$ $\sigma_{\max} = 0.3 \text{ MPa};$	$H = 1 \text{ m};$ $K_N = 100 \text{ m}^{-1};$ $\beta = 2; f = 0.5;$ $u_* = 0.005 \text{ m}.$

Changes in longitudinal stresses over time in the sections of the pipeline are shown in Fig.1. Curves 1–6 in Fig. 1 refer to pipeline sections $x = 5; 10; 15; 20; 25$ and 30 m and for $\gamma_2 = 1.1$. Here, in the initial section of soil $x=0$, load (8) with amplitude $\sigma_{\max} = 0.3 \text{ MPa}$ acts.

Fig. 1. Changes in longitudinal stresses over time in sections of an underground pipeline for $\gamma_2 = 1.1$.

In pipeline sections $x = 5; 10; 15; 20; 25$, and 30 m (Fig. 1), with a distance from the initial section $x=0$ (the stress-free section), there is a significant increase in the maximum values of the longitudinal stress ($\sigma_{1\max} = 96 \text{ MPa}$) compared to the stress amplitude

of the longitudinal wave in soil ($\sigma_{2\max} = 0.3 \text{ MPa}$). At high-frequency seismic waves in soil, this effect was not pronounced [3]. At $x = 5 \text{ m}$ (curve 1), stress amplitude $\sigma_{1\max}$ exceeds stress amplitude $\sigma_{2\max}$ in the initial section of soil by approximately 260 times.

At $x = 10$ m – by 315 times (curve 2), and at $x = 15; 20; 25$, and 30 m – by 320 times (curves 3–6). Consideration of strain characteristics of soil (γ_2) leads to multiple increases in the longitudinal stress in the pipeline sections. After reaching a certain asymptotic value $\sigma_{1\max}$, it remains constant. In this case, in the section of the pipeline $x=15$ m, the longitudinal stress reaches the limiting asymptotic value and then remains constant.

An increase in stress in the sections of the pipeline is a consequence of the transformation of the interaction force (friction) τ from a passive (resistance) force into an active (driving) force. In the case when the soil is in an undisturbed state, τ is almost always a passive force, which consequently leads to attenuation of the stress amplitude in the underground pipeline in all its sections [1, 2].

The calculation results showed that the maximum stress values in pipeline sections depend on the quantitative change in relative displacements, and, consequently, shear stresses in these sections.

Changes in stresses over time in fixed sections of the pipeline $x = 5; 10; 15; 20; 25$, and 30 m, obtained in calculations, showed that, compared with the case when $\gamma_2 = 1.1$, a qualitatively different pattern is observed. In this case, the stress amplitudes in the pipeline sections $x=5; 10; 15$, and 20 m grow all the time and become steady in section $x=25$ m.

Quantitatively, they differ by approximately 1.25 times from the case when $\gamma_2 = 1.1$. An increase in the maximum stress values in the pipeline sections for $\gamma_2 = 2$, is a consequence of an increase in the soil deformability. The process of steadying the maximum stress value, with a decrease in soil stiffness, increases. In this case, it is seen that the increase in the values of longitudinal stresses in the sections of the pipeline does not occur indefinitely.

Stresses in the same sections of the pipeline $x = 5; 10; 15; 20$, and 30 m for the case when $\gamma_2 = 4$, increases, tends to a steady state and in section $x = 30$ m reaches the value of 165 Mpa. This is 1.7 times more than the values obtained for $\gamma_2 = 1.1$ (70%), and 1.35 more than for $\gamma_2 = 2$ (35%). These results indicate that when the soil surrounding the pipeline is soft (not compacted, $\gamma_2 = 4$), the values of longitudinal stress in the pipeline increase significantly. In the case of compacted soil ($\gamma_2 = 1.1$, Fig. 1), the stress values are 1.7 times lower.

The results of estimating the values of longitudinal stresses in underground gas pipelines during the Gazli earthquake are given in [6]. According to [6], the maximum values of longitudinal stresses for main underground pipelines are $\sigma_{1\max} = (36.5 \div 85)$ Mpa.

Based on this, we can say that the calculated values of longitudinal stresses obtained in Fig. 1 are 12%

higher than the upper limit of stresses observed in pipelines during earthquakes. This confirms the correctness of the calculation results obtained in the study.

The calculation results show that an account for the strain characteristics of soil leads to new qualitative and quantitative results. In this article, we considered the effect of a plane longitudinal seismic wave at a frequency of 0.05 s^{-1} on an underground pipeline. The results of the calculations showed that with an increase in the frequency of seismic waves, the maximum value of the longitudinal stresses in the underground pipeline decreases.

Conclusion

The results obtained are the scientific basis for improving the technology of underground pipeline construction. To increase the seismic resistance of underground pipelines, it is necessary to increase the soil density and the cohesion force of soil surrounding the pipeline. Consequently, the stiffness (strength) of soil increases, and the relative displacement decreases, which ensures the formation of relatively low longitudinal stresses in the pipeline. This leads to a decrease in the probability of failure in underground pipelines being built in earthquake-prone regions.

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